
Rain Attenuation Analysis from System Operating at Ku and Ka Frequencies Bands

Osahenvemwen, O.A* , and Omorogiuwa, O

Department of Electrical and Electronic, Faculty of Engineering and Technology

Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Nigeria.

*Email: Osahenvemwenaustin@gmail.com

Received on May 12, 2017; revised on July 02, 2017; published on July 29, 2017

Abstract

This study presents rain attenuation analysis from System operating at Ku and Ka Frequencies Bands. Focused to determine the effects of weather conditions on propagation link performance property and quality of service render to customers. Recently, there is high demand of data rate, voice and video information have being on the increase due to industrial evolution and technological advancements. Satellite communication systems have witnessed various impairments which are considered in this study. Basic climate data were obtained from Meteorological Centre in Nigeria, for three years duration (from January 2013 to December 2015). Four geographical locations, Abuja, Benin City, Kano and Warri were considered in this study, in Nigeria. It is observed that Warri witnessed the highest rainfall followed by Benin City, Abuja and lastly by Kano. It is observed that the month of August witnessed the highest rainfall per each month followed by September and July at the year 2015. It was observed that rainfall distribution pattern possess a non-linear distribution pattern. Therefore, Empirical modelling was deployed; using excels software to determine the rainfall pattern. Based on the analysis, it was observed that rainfall followed exponential distribution pattern of rainfall. The basic parameters used in rain attenuation were highlighted with the corresponding attenuation characteristics such as rain intensity, rain height, effective path length, specific attenuation, rainy path length, slant path and horizontal projection specific attenuation were determined.

Keywords: Empirical modelling, Exponential, Rain Attenuation, and Rainfall Distribution Pattern

1 Introduction

The uses of data, voice, video information has being on the increase due to industrial evolution and technological advancements. The demand for multimedia applications, advancement in broadcast industries and quest for high quality of service performance has become imperative in this past decade. Also, with rising competition among internet and communication (voice) service providers to woo more subscribers with different applications and high quality of service render. Lastly, in view of the difficult terrain of some subscriber's locations, become necessary to use satellite technology to provide reliable quality of service. Radio wave propagation between terrestrial and earth space links are adversely affected by atmospheric gases, rain, and cloud, fog and atmospheric scintillation. The problem becomes more acute for system operating at frequencies above 10GHz (Ku, Ka and V bands). Nigeria is located in the tropics unlike the temperate environments such as Europe and North America. The effects of the troposphere in micro wave signals will be most severe in the tropics because of high occurrence of rainfall, high temperature, high relative humidity and high rain intensities which lead to a more severe signal attenuation and outage than what is experienced in the temperate region. Unfortunately, most communication satellite equipment supplied to Africa are designed based on propagation measurement made in Europe and North America, which may not meet

the minimum availability standard that can cope with hash weather experienced in the tropics.

The difficult terrains such as swamp areas, riverine areas are associated with heavy rainfall. The C-band (6/4 GHz) satellites communication were deployed, but due to some drawbacks associated, such as bandwidth limitation (within 500 MHz - 1000 MHz), interference due to congestion, narrow beam cannot be transmitted and direct reception in TVs at home uses bigger sizes of parabolic dishes (Sapna, 2008). Which necessitate, the use of Ku band (under k- band 14/12 GHz), Ka band (after k-band 30/20 GHz) and V band (70/55 GHz) take the centre stage of satellite communication due to higher performance, relatively congestion free. The satellite communications using frequencies of higher than 10 GHz (such as Ku band, Ka band and V band) are affected by various propagation impairments such as rain attenuation, delay, cloud attenuation, Tropospheric scintillation, Ionospheric scintillation, water vapor attenuation, and rain and ice depolarization (Sridhar, *et al* 2012, Osahenvemwen, 2013).

Rainfall or raindrop results in attenuation of radio waves by scattering and by absorption of energy from the wave and increase with increase in frequency, which degrades the reliability and performance of the communication link. (Sapna, 2008). Rain effects are dependent on frequency, rain rate, rain drop size distribution and drop shape, which are determined by the type of rain witnessed in this region under investigation (Yee Hui Lee_ and Stefan Winkler).The country Nigeria lie in tropical heavy rain regions with coordinate of latitude 10⁰ 00'N longitude 8⁰00'E with total area of 923,768 square kilometers. It located within the equator

and tropic of cancer the latitude of Nigeria fall within the tropical zone but the climate conditions are not entirely tropical in nature. The climate condition varies in most parts of the country. In the north the climate condition is arid and to the south there is an equatorial type of climate. Therefore, due to this variation in climate condition on different geographical locations in Nigeria, it is important to carry out holistic study on this environment.

There are two common rain types, which are convective rain and stratiform rain. The Convective rain arises from vertical atmospheric motions resulting in vertical transport and mixing. The convective rain flow occurs in a cell whose horizontal extent is usually several kilometers. The cell may be isolated or embedded in a thunderstorm region associated with a passing weather front. Because of the motion of the front and the sliding motion of the cell along the front, the high rain rate usually only lasts for several minutes. These rains are the most common sources of high rain rate events. While, the stratiform rain typically shows a stratified horizontal extent of hundreds of kilometers, durations exceeding one hour, and low rain rates of less than 25 mm/hr. For communication applications, stratiform rain occurs for sufficiently long periods of time that a link margin may be required to exceed the resulting attenuation. Stratiform rain covers large geographic areas, and the spatial distribution of total rainfall is expected to be uniform. During stratiform type of rain the point, where the frozen water or ice begins to melt and forms rain, is the 0°C isotherm height (Ojo et al). Likewise the rain rate averaged over several hours is expected to be rather similar for ground sites located up to tens of kilometers apart (Yee Hui Lee_ and Stefan Winkler). The two major causes of rain fade are:

Absorption – water molecules in a rain droplet absorb portions or all of the signal energy of the passing radio wave. With shorter wavelength, there will be more interaction between the radio wave and water molecules, leading to increased in energy losses.

Scattering – this is a physical process, caused by either refraction or diffraction, in which the direction of the radio wave deviates from its original path as it passes through a medium containing raindrops. This disperses the energy of the signal from its initial travel direction. The accumulation of these different reactions ultimately leads to a decrease in the level of received signal, thus resulting in rain attenuation (Osahenmwemwen, 2013). In addition, rain Attenuation is being affected by variation of frequency, location, polarization and rainfall rate.

2 Satellite Propagation Technique

The problems observed on satellite transmission are due to absorption from the cloud, ice, rain attenuation due to snow, hail and fog. Satellite radio waves are propagated through ionosphere, troposphere and stratosphere. The ionosphere is the upper part of the atmosphere where sufficient ionization takes place, to influence radio wave propagation. The ionosphere usually consist three layers D, E and F region. D region is the lowest of the ionosphere layers, it extends from approximately 50 to 90km with the maximum electron of about 10⁹/M³ occurring between 75 and 80km in the day time. As the electron concentration in the D region is very low, it tends to have little effect on light frequency wave. E region extends from 90 to 140km and peak electron concentration occurs between 100 and 110km (Sanjeev, 2011).

Electron densities in F₀ region vary with the 11years sunspot cycle. Electron concentrations drop by a factor of about 100 at night in the E region. F region has the highest electron densities of the normal ionosphere. In the day time it normally consist of two parts F₁ and F₂. F₁ is largely disappear at night but has a peak density of about 1.5 × 10¹¹/M³ at noon the minimum of the solar cycle F₂ has the highest peak electron densities of ionosphere and it remains higher than in D and E region. Reflection from F₂ layer is the major factor in higher frequency communication which formally handled a large fraction of long distance especially transoceanic, communication (Muhammad.et al.2011). Since the ionization is mainly caused by solar radiation, it is dependent on the location, time of the day, season and sunspot. Radio wave’s propagation through ionosphere experienced different attenuation at frequencies above 10GHZ. As reported in literature, atmosphere contains force electrons, ions and molecules which interact with radio waves dependent strongly on frequency, so as the frequency increases, the effect of attenuation increases.

The propagation factors that affect Ku and Ka bands satellite links communication includes, rain attenuation, depolarization due to rain and ice, antenna wetting, gaseous absorption cloud attenuation, wetting layers attenuation and tropospheric scintillation. In several rains fade compensation approaches can be considered at three major characteristics of the propagation factor as followed: rang of signal fading (dB), rate of signal fluctuation (dB/sec) and frequency dependence (scaling)

3 Methods

This study was on rain attenuation analysis from system operating at Ku and Ka frequencies bands. Using Nigeria as a case study, which lie in tropical heavy rain regions with coordinate of latitude 10° 00’ N and longitude 8° 00’ E with total area of 923,768 square kilometers. Its located within the equator and tropic of cancer the latitude of Nigeria fall within the tropical zone but the climate conditions are not entirely tropical in nature. Four geographical locations were considered within the country such are Abuja, Benin City, Kano and Warri, were considered in Nigeria. The daily rainfall data were obtained from Meteorological Center in Nigeria, for period of three year (from January 2013 to December 2015) for four different geography locations in Nigeria. Rainfall distribution pattern was determine. Empirical modeling and comparison between linear and exponential distribution pattern of rainfall for Benin City were considered in this research. Analysis of rain attenuation characteristics such has rain intensity, Effective path length, specific attenuation, rainy path length, rain height, slang path, horizontal projection specific attenuation were determined based on the ITU-R prediction model for various region based on obtained data and 12 GHz as operating frequency.

Fig1: Map of Nigeria shown the four different locations under investigation

3.1 Data presentation

The daily rainfall for three years for four different geography locations in Nigeria such are Abuja, Benin City, Kano and Warri, were considered

Table 1: Average Rainfalls mm (inches) for Three Year, Four Different Locations

Mon ths	Abuja			Kano			Warri			Benin city		
	2013	2014	2015	2013	2014	2015	2013	2014	2015	2013	2014	2015
Janu	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.5	2.9	0.0	0.4	2.7	0.9
Feb	1.4	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.6	3.3	7.2	1.9	6.2
Mar	0.9	2.2	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.9	4.7	4.5	4.1	4.2	5.9
April	4.5	5.2	0.8	1.5	0.6	0.0	6.9	5.9	7.9	6.7	7.1	3.6

May	4.0	7.7	7.7	1.3	2.4	0.0	7.5	11.5	10.8	10.1	8.1	6.7
June	5.4	5.8	5.8	2.6	3.0	2.3	15.3	10.2	16.0	8.5	8.1	13.3
July	6.2	2.4	2.4	5.1	15.5	4.9	16.0	6.3	6.1	12.6	8.8	12.5
Aug	5.9	17.9	4.5	13.3	16.4	15.6	5.9	11.3	20.2	5.4	13.1	7.1
Sept	9.1	7.0	4.4	5.9	6.2	3.9	6.2	13.7	11.1	18.8	12.3	11.4
Octo	6.5	7.0	7.0	0.3	0.6	0.3	4.9	15.3	16.9	10.9	11.8	8.8
Nov	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.8	8.4	7.6	3.5	5.4	0.6
Dec	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.7	0.0	1.9	1.1	0.4

Table 2 Climatological parameters of the stations under investigation

S/ N	Locati ons	Latitude	Longitud e	Height above sea level (Meters)	Elevation angle
1	Abuja	9° 12' N	7° 11' E	476 meters (0.476 KM or 1561 ft)	60.0°
2	Benin City	9° 30' N	2° 15' E	86 meters (0.086 KM or 282ft)	60.0°
3	Kano	12° 02'N	08° 30'E	488 Meters (0.488 km) or 1,601 ft	30.0°
4	Warri	5° . 52' N	5° . 75' E	21 meters (0.021 KM or 69 ft)	60.0°

Source: [http://dateandtime.info/citycoordinate php, 2015].

(Note) Elevation above sea level: 484 m = 1587 ft

3.2 Basic rain characteristics that affect satellite communication

Rain attenuation is defined as the product of specific attenuation (dB/km) and the effective propagation path length (km). The product of path reduction factor and the physical path length of a microwave link are referred to as the effective path length. The strength of satellite signal may be degraded or reduced under rain conditions; in particular radio waves above 10 GHz are subject to attenuation by molecular absorption and rain. Presence of rain drops can severely degrade the reliability and performance of communication links. Attenuation due to rain effect is a function of various parameters including elevation angle, carrier frequency, height of earth station, latitude of earth station and rain fall rate. The primary parameters, however, are drop-size distribution and the number of drops that are present in the volume shared by the wave with the rain. It is important to note that, attenuation is determined not by how much rain has fallen but the rate at which it is falling. The propagation loss due to rain is given by:

$$L = 10 \log \frac{P_r(0)}{P_r(r)} \tag{1}$$

Where P_0 is the signal power before the rain region, P_r is the signal power after the rain region, and r is the path length through the rain region. The propagation loss due to rain attenuation is usually expressed by specific attenuation γ in decibels per kilometer, so propagation loss is:

$$L = \gamma l_r \tag{2}$$

Where γ is specific attenuation in dB/km and l_r is rain path length in km. Based on ITU-R specific attenuation model. It is found that γ depends only on rainfall rate, measured in millimeters per hour. From this model, the usual form of expressing γ is:

$$\gamma = KB^\alpha [dB/KM] \tag{3}$$

Where K and α is frequency dependent coefficients.

Attenuation can be obtained from direct measurements or predicted from the knowledge of rain rate.

In determining rain attenuation along the slant-path of satellite communication required the rain parameters as followed:

- f : the frequency of operation in GHz, (12 GHz)
- θ : the elevation angle to the satellite, in degrees, (in Table 2)
- ϕ : the latitude of the ground station, in degrees N and S, (in Table 2)
- h_s : the height of the ground station above sea level, in km, (in Table 2)
- R_e : effective radius of the Earth (8 500 km),

$R_{0.01}$: point rainfall rate for the location of interest for 0.01% of an average year (mm/hr).

Firstly to compute the rain attenuation along the slant-path in satellite communication system is summarized as follows:

Step 1: Determine the rain height, h_R (KM) from the recommendation ITU-R P.839 as

$$h_R = h_0 + 0.36KM \tag{4}$$

Where h_0 is the 0° C isotherm height above mean sea level at the desired location

Step 2 Determine the slant-path length (L_S) km

$$L_S = \frac{h_r - h_s}{\sin \theta} \text{ for } \theta \geq 5^\circ \tag{5}$$

Also, it given as

$$L_S = \frac{2(h_r - h_s)}{(\sin^2 \theta + \frac{2(h_r - h_s)}{R_e})^{\frac{1}{2}}} \text{ for } \theta \leq 5^\circ \tag{6}$$

Where θ is Elevation angle in degrees, h_s is the height of the location above sea level in Km, and h_r is the rain height in Km.

The horizontal projection is then expressed as:

$$L_G = L_S \cos \theta \tag{7}$$

Step 3: Determine the rain rate at 0.01% for the location of interest (Warri) over an average year. In this work, 62mm/hr from is used to derive rain rate at one-minute integration time at 0.01% of exceeded from long-term local data.

Step 4: Calculate the specific attenuation, γ_R , by using the frequency dependent regression coefficients provided in

ITU-R P.838 Recommendation $R_{0.01}$ and using the following Equation

$$\gamma_R = K(R_{0.01})^\alpha \text{ dB/km} \tag{8}$$

K and α are regression coefficients which depend on the frequency, polarization, raindrop size distribution and temperature and obtained using,

$$K = \frac{K_H K_V + (K_H - K_V) \cos^2 \theta \cos(2t)}{2} \tag{9}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{K_H \alpha_H + K_V \alpha_V + (K_H \alpha_H - K_V \alpha_V) \cos^2 \theta \cos(2t)}{2K} \tag{10}$$

Where t is the polarization tilt angle relative to horizontal and θ is the path elevation angle. The polarization tilt angle $t = 90$ for vertical polarization and $t=0$ for horizontal polarization while circular polarization is given as $t = 45$. The frequency dependent coefficients k_H , k_v , α_H and α_v are obtained for both horizontal and vertical polarization over frequencies of 1-400 GHz.

Step 5: Determine the horizontal reduction factor or horizontal path adjustment factor, $r_{0.01}$ at 0.01% probability and expressed as:

$$r_{0.01} = \frac{1}{1 + 0.78 \sqrt{\frac{L_G \gamma_R}{f} - 0.38(1 - e^{-2L_G})}} \tag{11}$$

Note: L_G is the horizontal projection as determined in Step 2 and f is the operating frequency measured in GHz.

Step 6: calculate the adjusted rainy path length L_R (KM) through rain using

$$L_R = \frac{L_G r_{0.01}}{\cos \theta} \text{ for } \xi > 0 \tag{12}$$

$$L_S = \frac{h_R - h_s}{\sin \theta} \text{ for } \xi \leq 0 \tag{13}$$

$$\xi = \tan^{-1} \frac{h_R - h_s}{L_G r_{0.01}} \text{ Degrees} \tag{14}$$

Step 7 obtain the vertical reduction factor or vertical adjustment factor, $v_{0.01}$, for 0.01% of the time by using

$$V_{0.01} = \frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{\sin \theta} \left[31 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\theta}{1+X}} \right) \frac{\sqrt{L_R \gamma_R}}{f^2} - 0.45 \right]} \tag{15}$$

Where $X = 36 - \phi / \theta$, for $\phi / \theta < 36^\circ$

$X = 0$, for $\phi / \theta > 36^\circ$

Step 8: The effective path length through rain L_E is then computed from:

$$L_E = L_R V_{0.01} \text{ KM} \tag{18}$$

Step 9: Calculate the predicted attenuation exceeded for 0.01% of an average year.

$$A_{0.01} = \gamma_R L_E \text{ DB} \tag{19}$$

Step 10: The estimated attenuation to be exceeded for the other percentages of an average year, in the range 0.001% to 10% may then be estimated using $A_{0.01}$ as

$$A_p = A_{0.01} \left(\frac{p}{0.01}\right)^{-[0.655+0.03 \ln(p)-0.045 \ln(A_{0.01})-\beta \sin \theta(1-p)]} \tag{20}$$

Where p is the percentage probability of interest and β is given by

$$\text{For } p \geq 1\%, \beta = 0 \tag{21}$$

$$\text{For } p < 1\%, \beta = 0 \text{ if } \theta \geq 36^\circ \tag{22}$$

$$\beta = -0.005 (\theta / -36) \text{ for } \theta \geq 25^\circ \text{ and } \theta \leq 36^\circ \tag{23}$$

$$\beta = -0.005 (\theta / -36) + 1.8 - 4.25 \sin \theta \tag{24}$$

$$\text{For } \theta < 25^\circ \text{ and } \theta < 36^\circ \tag{25}$$

Table 3. Various rainfall rates with different % time exceeded (Warri)

S/N	% Time exceeded	Rainfall Rate (mm/hr)	Attenuation (dB)
1	0.001%	114.36	35.45
2	0.01%	62.00	16.35
3	0.1%	17.13	3.22
4	1%	1.94	0.21
5	10%	0	0.0

In this analysis some parameter were assumed to be able to determine the rain attenuation parameters, such operating frequency at 12 GHz, and other basic parameters obtained are from Table 2.

Table 4. Rainfall Parameters Related to Ku and Ka frequencies bands.

S/N	Locations under investigation	Duration of years	Rainfall (mm)	rain height	Effective path length, (Km)
1	Abuja	2013-2015	9.25	4.17 km	12.03
2	Benin City	2013-2015	12.36	3.78 km	10.23
3	Kano	2013-2015	8.35	4.18 km	12.11
5	Warri	2013-2015	13.14	3.71 km	10.07

Determine the slant-path length (L_s) km or effective path length

$$L_s = \frac{h_r - h_s}{\sin \theta} \text{ for } \theta \geq 5^\circ$$

$$L_s = \frac{3.78 - 0.086}{\sin 60^\circ} = 10.23 \text{ km} \text{ For Benin City location}$$

The slant-path length (L_s) km or effective path length is used to determine the rain attenuation in satellite communication system.

4 Data Analysis, Result and Discussion

The data obtained from Nigeria metrological centre from 2013 to 2015 for four different geographical locations are analysis using Microsoft excel software to determine various Figures.

Fig 2: total rain fall for three years for four different geographical locations The daily rainfalls were obtained from metrological centre in Nigeria, from the three years data, from 2013 to 2015 were considered for four geographical locations. Warri and Benin City are from the south of Nigeria, while Abuja was from the centre part of Nigeria and lastly Kano was located in north part of Nigeria. It was observed that warri witnessed the highest rainfall has shown in Fig 2, followed by Benin City, Abuja and lastly by Kano.

Fig 3 cascaded of rainfall into yearly bases on the four different geographical locations

The rainfalls were cascaded into yearly bases in the four different geographical locations in Nigeria. From the Fig 3, the year rainfalls were compared; it was observed that Benin City, Kano and Abuja witnessed lower rainfall throughout the 2015 year, while Warri witnessed the heaviest rainfall in 2015. In Fig 4 showed the rainfalls in four different locations in relative to years and months. It was observed that the month of August witnessed the highest rainfall per each month followed by September and July

Fig 4 Rainfalls in Four Different Locations with respectively Years and Months

In Fig 5 presents the rainfall distribution pattern for four different geographical locations, the rainfall were capture throughout the days and the months in 2015 years and was compared with rainfall distribution pattern of Benin City location, using different years presented in Fig 6. It was observed that rainfall distribution pattern is non-linear distribution pattern.

Fig 5 the rainfall Distribution pattern for Benin City for three years

4.1 Empirical modeling

Empirical modeling refers to any kind of computer modeling based on empirical observations rather than on mathematically describable relationships of the system modeled. Based on the data obtained, and developing empirical model, deploying micro software using excel package, the resultant output were presented in Fig 7 and Fig 8. This empirical model was developed based on rainfall data obtained from Benin City location for three years. The distribution pattern was examined as Exponential distribution pattern and the resultant equations were presented in Fig 7, similarly linear distribution pattern was considered in Fig 8. The comparison of between Exponential distribution pattern and linear distribution pattern are presented in Table 4.

Fig 7: Empirical model based on exponential distribution pattern

Fig 8 Empirical model based on linear distribution pattern

Table 5: the comparison between linear and exponential distribution pattern of rainfall for Benin City

S / N	Years	Linear Distribution Pattern		Exponential Distribution Pattern	
		Resultant Equation	R ² -Squared value	Resultant Equation	R ² -Squared value
1	2013	$y = 0.28x + 5660$	$R^2 = 0.040$	$Y = 3.344e^{0.07x}$	$R^2 = 0.067$
2	2014	$y = 0.389x + 4.577$	$R^2 = 0.112$	$y = 4.375e^{0.038x}$	$R^2 = 0.031$
3	2015	$y = 0.013x + 8.36$	$R^2 = 0.000$	$y = 6.647e^{-0.07x}$	$R^2 = 0.047$

The resultant outputs from empirical modeling are presented in Table 5, which involves the comparison between linear and exponential distribution pattern of rainfall for Benin City for duration of three years (2013-2015) average rainfall. It was observed that exponential distribution

pattern of rainfall were more consisted, compared to the result obtained from linear distribution rain pattern in Table 5.

Therefore the exponential distribution pattern Equation is presented in Equation (26).

$$y = 4.375e^{0.038x} \quad (26)$$

Y represents the average rainfall from 2013 to 2015; x represents the various months of the year. The resultant R²- squared value obtained is 0.031.

4.2 Analysis of rain attenuation parameters in respect to satellite communication

Nigeria is a tropical region that lies between the geographical area of 4°N, 3°E and 14°N, 15°E in the South-Eastern edge of the West African region. It is characterized by rainy and dry

4.2.1 Analysis of rain attenuation parameters in respect to satellite communication

Nigeria is a tropical region that lies between the geographical area of 4°N, 3°E and 14°N, 15°E in the South-Eastern edge of the West African region. It is characterized by rainy and dry seasons. The rainy season (between the months of April and October) is heavily influenced by an air mass originating from the South Atlantic Ocean, known as the South-West (monsoon) wind or the Tropical Maritime (MT) air mass, while the dry season (between November and March) are accompanied by a dust laden air mass from the Sahara desert, known as Harmat-tan or the Tropical Continental (CT) air mass. Harmattans (between December and February) are the dry, hot-by-day and cold-by-night dust-laden North-East wind, which is usually associated with the variable intensification of the sub-tropical anticyclone. Nigeria, like any other tropical region is characterized mostly by convective rainfall types (Convective, Monsoon Precipitation and Tropical Storm).

5 Conclusion

Most satellite services are offered at C band frequencies, but a lot of interest applications emerged in deploying Ku and ka-band satellites. The advantages offered, by ku and ka band satellite services include terrain independence and large coverage areas etc. The congestion experienced at lower frequency bands satellite, due to high demand for diverse services and increased bandwidth used by voice calls were explored by higher frequency bands (ku and ka band). The major drawback experienced in operating at such a higher frequencies (Ka-band and above), is signal distortion result from free space and rainfall. In this study, the rain attenuation is calculated, for different rainfall rates and exceedence percentages under the investigated area. It is observed that attenuation increases as rainfall rates increase. However, rainfall attenuation is strongly dependent on two factors as followed: operating frequency and the local rain rate. Also, the effective path length for each region is determined and it is dependent on frequency and elevation angle. The effective path length depends strongly on elevation angle and operating frequency of the satellite. Also the vertical polarization produces less rain attenuation than horizontal polarization at Ku and Ka band and the rainfall distribution pattern followed exponential distribution pattern under area investigated. Further study, can be carried out in this area by developing models for rain attenuation parameters in corresponding to the locations under investigation.

References

- Badron, K. Ismail, A.F. Islam, M.R. Tharek, A.R and Din, J. (2011). Rain Attenuation Prediction Model for Tropical V-band Satellite Earth link, International Conference on Telecommunication Technology and Applications Proc .of CSIT, Vol.5 IACSIT Press, Singapore.
- <http://www.brifannica.comn/EBchecked/topic/524891/satellite-communication,Satellite communication>, accessed on 4th July, 2013.
- <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/communications- satellite, communication satellite>, accessed on 6th June, 2013.
- <http://www.brifannica.comn/EBchecked/topic/524891/satellite-communication, Satellite communication>, accessed on 4th July, 2013.
- <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/warri, Warri>, accessed on 7th July, 2013.

- <http://jwcn.eurasipjournals.com/content/2012/1/189>, Islam et al. EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking 2012, 2012:189, accessed 26 /6/2013.
- <http://www.nairaland.com/7715/official-free-to-air>, Office thread of free to air satellite TV (part 1), accessed on 21st July, 2013.
- <http://www.nimetring.org/uploads/publication/Annual,2010> climate review Mkparu, accessed on 6th July,2013.
- [http:// www.map- streeviewcomNigeria/warri;Warri-map](http://www.map- streeviewcomNigeria/warri;Warri-map), accessed on 9th July, 2013
- [http://www.nimet.org/uploads/publication/nimet, Seasonal rainfall prediction \(SRP\)](http://www.nimet.org/uploads/publication/nimet, Seasonal rainfall prediction (SRP)), accessed on 2nd August, 2013.
- Kirtay, S. (2002). Broadband satellite system technologies for effective use of the 12-30GHz radio spectrum, Electronics and Communication Engineering Journal page 79-89.
- Isikwue, B. C., Ikoyo, A.H. and Utah, E.U. (2013). Analysis of rainfall rates and attenuations for Line-of-sight EHF/SHF radio communication links over Makurdi, Nigeria, Research Journal of Earth and Planetary Sciences Vol. 3(2) pp. 60 – 74.
- Malinga, P. A. Owolawi, and T. J. O. Afullo, (2013). Estimation of Rain Attenuation at C, Ka, Ku and V Bands for Satellite Links in South Africa, PIERS Proceedings, Taipei,28,
- Muhammad Zubair, Zaffar Haider, Shahid, A. Khan, Jamal Nasir, (2011). Atmospheric influences on satellite communications COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Islamabad (1,2,3), COMSATS Institute of Information Technology, Abbott Abad (4), Przegład Elektrotechniczny (Electrical Review), ISSN 0033-2097, R. 87 NR 5.
- Ojo, J. S. and Ajewole, M. O. (2008). Rain rate and Rain attenuation prediction for satellite communication in Ku and Ka bands over Nigeria, Progress in Electromagnetics Research B, Vol. 5, 207–223.
- Osahenwemwen, O.A. and Omorogiuwa, O. (2013), Effect of Rain on Satellite Communication Networks in Nigeria: Case Study of Warri Town, Journal of Nigeria Association of Mathematical Physics, Volume 25, No2, Pp107-114. (<http://namjournals.org/abstracts/vol25abstract.pdf>)
- Sanjeev, S. J., Suresh and Ganesh Madhan, M., (2011). An Experimental Study of Rain Attenuation at Ku Band Frequencies for an Earth Space Path over Chennai, International Symposium on Devices MEMS, Intelligent Systems & Communication (ISDMISC) Proceedings published by International Journal of Computer Applications (IJCA), page 46-49.
- Sridhar, M. K., Padma Raju, and Ch. Srinivasa Rao, (2012). Estimation of Rain Attenuation based on ITU-R Model in Guntur (A.P), India, ACEEE Int. J. on Communications, Vol. 03, No. 03,
- Vatcharakorn, Netharn, Surasee Prahmkaw and Siriwaddhanah Pongpadpinit, (2013). Improve Receive Signal over Ku-Band Satellite Communications Based on Fuzzy Logic, International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research, Volume 4, Issue 1, ISSN 2229-5518, Pp 45-48.
- Yussuff Abayomi, I.O, Hisham Haji Khamis, (2012). Rain Attenuation Modelling and Mitigation in the Tropics: Brief Review, International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE), Vol.2, No.6, Pp. 748-757.
- Yasuyuki Maekawa, Tadashi Fujiwara1, Yoshiaki Shibagaki,(2006). Effects of Tropical Rainfall to the Ku-Band Satellite Communications Links at the Equatorial Atmosphere Radar Observatory, Journal of the Meteorological Society of Japan, Vol. 84A, Pp. 211-225.